

Point of Contact Information

JEFF WALTER

jeff.walter@nasa.gov

Atmospheric Science Data Center

NASA Langley Research Center

Hampton, VA 23666

Background

EDUCATION

2005: M.S. in Computer Science, College of William and Mary, Williamsburg, VA

1994: M.S. in Geology, University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, NC

1991: B.S. in Geology, Virginia Tech, Blacksburg, VA

EMPLOYMENT

2016 – Present. Deputy Head/Science Data Systems Architecture and Engineering Lead, NASA Langley Research Center, Atmospheric Science Data Center

2011 – 2016. Deputy Project Manager/Technical, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center

1999 – 2011. Science Data Systems Engineer, SSAI/NASA Langley Research Center

RELEVANT EXPERIENCE

Mr. Walter is the Deputy Head and the Science Data Systems Architecture and Engineering Lead at the NASA Langley Research Center's Atmospheric Science Data Center (ASDC). He currently leads a multi-disciplinary team working to evolve and improve ASDC's science data production, management, and distribution services. He has extensive experience with designing, implementing, operating, and managing science data processing, archive, and distribution systems. He also has a long history of successfully teaming with and supporting the data management and processing needs of multiple NASA science and instrument teams including MAIA, MISR, MOPITT, CALIPSO, TES, CERES, SAGE III, SMAP, Operation IceBridge, and others in both engineering and project management roles. A major focus of his current work is on leading the development of a next-generation mission science data processing system using cloud-enabling technologies.

Mr. Walter also has significant technical project management experience. He was formerly the Deputy Project Manager/Technical for NASA's Earth Science Data and Information System (ESDIS) Project at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center. In this role, he provided project management support as well as technical direction, guidance, decision authority, and oversight to the continual evolution of the Earth Observing System Data and Information System (EOSDIS), which includes NASA's twelve Distributed Active Archive Centers (DAACs). He also successfully managed a multi-year, multi-million-dollar project sponsored by the White House Office of Science and Technology (OSTP).

Topic Area: Data Processing Architecture

At the ASDC, we are building and will be operating a new science data processing system to support the Multi-Angle Imager for Aerosols (MAIA) mission. However, the architecture of the system is designed to be able to support science data processing for other missions with a single system instantiation. Details are below.

Key components/features of the architecture

- Platform – The system is implemented in Red Hat OpenShift, which is an enterprise Kubernetes container orchestration platform. The advantage of using this technology is that it is cloud-native, highly scalable, and supported by modern CI/CD practices.
- Graph database – We use a graph database, Neo4j, as the backend database. Complex science data processing flows lend themselves naturally to being represented by a directed acyclic graph. We use this database to manage processing state and as a queryable repository of processing history and provenance information. Graph query APIs are implemented using GraphQL.
- Common functions and services – Even though they are partitioned and implemented differently in each system, all science data processing systems need to perform certain functions. These include, but are not necessarily limited to, computational resource management, job execution, cache data management, interfacing with input data sources, and interfacing with a DAAC for submission of output data products. By having generic implementations with well-defined interfaces, these services can be utilized by more than one mission at a time and easily scaled accordingly.
- Mission-specific functions and services – While certain things can be genericized, each mission will inevitably have requirements that are unique. The primary place where this occurs is in the logic and requirements related to defining individual PGE jobs and the selection and definition of a job's specific inputs and outputs. The term of art we use for this is “production rules.” Our system has been designed so that the production rule implementation is isolated from the rest of the system in its own service. This would allow another mission to either swap out or simply add in their own production rule service as long as the interfaces to the other services are adhered to. Even if a mission did not reuse any of the code from the MAIA production rule service, we feel that the design concept could potentially be useful as a reference architecture for this functionality.
- Component interaction – All of the individual components interact via the widely deployed, open source RabbitMQ message broker. RabbitMQ supports several messaging protocols including the AMQP 0-9-1 standard. The message payloads are all JSON-based and have well-defined models for each component. For the sake of simplicity, we rely on the DAAC as the sole source for input data and acquire that data via https. Submission to the DAAC is currently via the SIPS PDR protocol but that will likely change to the https-based Science Data Transfer Protocol (SDTP) in the future.

Relevance to the Study

The MAIA data processing system provides an example of a scalable, flexible, architecture that leverages modern, mature, cloud-ready technologies. It has the potential to facilitate reuse for a set of common functions while allowing the flexibility to implement mission-specific complexities in a way that decouples them from the rest of the system.

Topic Area: Open Science

Software Release

The NASA software release process has traditionally been a significant barrier to the open-source science objectives of making data and code as transparent to the public as quickly as possible. Not only has the turnaround time often averaged a year in length but dissecting the licenses of included third-party software has hampered efforts. While only including open-source, third-party software is the smoothest path to releasing NASA software as open source, not all open-source licenses are created equal. In particular, the ubiquitous GNU General Public License (GNU GPL) has proven problematic. Broadening the acceptance of more open-source licenses, including GNU GPL, would make it easier to develop open-source software.

Software Engineering Best Practices

Because NASA is not primarily a software engineering business entity, the utilization of software engineering best practices is distributed unevenly to say the least. Scientific research is increasingly reliant on custom software, which is often not well documented or managed, let alone shared outside of one's organization. The NASA workforce and the scientific community in general need better training and incentivization to utilize software engineering best practices.

One potential resource to facilitate this is the Software Carpentry curriculum. This organization of volunteer instructors specializes in teaching two-day software engineering workshops that cover the basics of:

- Programming in Python or R
- Unix terminal and shell basics
- Git/GitHub

Git, especially, is a skill that is required in order to be able to exchange information in an open-source science framework. Furthermore, the programming language component of Software Carpentry encourages the use of Jupyter Notebooks, which are a compact way to write data analysis code, display the output, and craft markdown verbiage alongside, in one easily shareable document. Instilling knowledge of this technology could expedite report-writing and sharing within our workforce and among our stakeholders.

In a similar fashion, container technologies package software and dependencies to run an application, and it is worth cultivating a better knowledge base for this technology as well. Eventually, a centralized container repository could be populated and cataloged in an organized way, so that NASA Earth Science or SMD could continue to leverage previous work to expedite progress on new software.

In summary, we encourage NASA to continue to vigorously pursue ways to cultivate and enable strong software engineering practices and principles across our science communities. First, it will help ensure that we continue to have sound scientific output and results. Second, it will ensure that the public continues to have confidence in our output and results. Publication of poorly written or engineered code could potentially have an impact on that confidence.

Topic Area: Component Technologies

Storage

Choice of file formats could greatly affect the user experience of data products in the cloud. The HDF Group's Highly Scalable Data Service (HSDS), for instance, is a means of data storage that specializes in improving parallelized reading and writing of data. With any number of users accessing cloud-based data at any given time, this format should be considered as a candidate storage format, which also extends seamlessly from common Earth Science data formats HDF5 and netCDF4 and runs on the major commercial cloud platforms. Zarr file format, in a similar way, improves speed of access (including parallel access) to cloud-based data. Rather than a service, however, it is a file format itself, that can wrap an existing HDF4/netCDF5 file seamlessly for transformation into its object cloud storage.

Containerization

More and more mission teams are containerizing their algorithm executables. With the ability to package all software, library, and version dependencies into a single discrete unit, the portability benefits are clear and this relieves the burden of having to keep the development and runtime environments in lockstep configurations. Up to this point in time, Docker has been the most widely used containerization technology by far. However, a container runtime environment called Singularity (<https://sylabs.io>) is gaining traction in the scientific computing community. One reason is that, in addition to the well-known benefits of Docker and containerization in general, Singularity has native support for many of the technologies and tools used in traditional HPC environments. However, more importantly, it seems to have a more robust security model. Specifically, Singularity limits a user's ability to escalate their privileges within a running container. Their privileges within the container will be the same as their privileges on the host in which they are running, which is not always necessarily the case with Docker. In fact, the NASA LaRC OCIO's HPC cluster only has Singularity available, not Docker, for this very reason. Especially in an environment where container images will likely be built and delivered from multiple different places, this is something worth considering.

Graph databases

As noted in the Data Processing Architecture section above, ASDC is using the Neo4j graph database (<https://neo4j.com>) to model and capture the complex details of the MAIA science data production flow. Graph databases have number of potential applications in this context. They can be useful for quickly determining the impacts of a change or failure in the system. Root cause analysis of failures can be performed quickly by tracing back dependencies in a simple way. The schema is highly flexible and additional node types, relationships, or properties can be added without disrupting existing functionality. There is the potential to optimize resource allocation and utilization at an enterprise level by analyzing the relationships over time between jobs, the data they touch and produce, and the resources they consume. Finally, it is our understanding NASA's ESDIS project is currently exploring the use of graph database technology to support a data user recommendation engine and overall general knowledge graph. Connecting a science data processing database to a broader ESDIS one has the potential to offer unprecedented insight and a holistic view into the relationships and pathways from acquisition to processing to DAACs to users to publications.